

Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of some 1-Phenyl-3,5-diaryl-2-pyrazolines and 3,5-Diaryl-2-isoxazolines^ψ

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Manuscript received 12 August 1991, revised 28 June 1993, accepted 30 June 1993

Pyrazolines and isoxazolines are important nitrogen containing heterocycles possessing diverse biological activities¹. In view of this, we now report the synthesis of some new heterocycles, viz. 1,3,5-triaryl-2-pyrazolines (2) and 3,5-diaryl-2-isoxazolines (3).

Condensation of the appropriate acetophenone and aromatic aldehydes in presence of ethanolic potassium hydroxide yielded the corresponding 1,3-diarylchalcones² (1). The chalcones (1) possess an α,β -unsaturated grouping in the molecules and react with phenylhydrazine to yield phenylhydrazones which immediately rearrange to the corresponding isomeric 1-phenyl-3-(2''-hydroxy-4''-n-butoxy-5''-bromophenyl)-5-aryl-2-pyrazolines (2) in the presence of acetic acid³. Again compounds 1 react with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in presence of ethanolic potassium hydroxide to yield the corresponding 3-(2''-hydroxy-4''-n-butoxy-5''-bromophenyl)-5-aryl-2-isoxazolines³(3)(Scheme 1). The structural assignment of the compounds was based on elemental analysis and ir and nmr spectral data. The antibacterial activity of 2 and 3 has been studied by cup-plate method⁴.

Ir spectra of compounds 1a-e reveal bands at 1 645-1 635 (C=O) and 1 580-1 570 cm^{-1} (C=C). Due to chelation, the band is not observed at 3 500-3 300 cm^{-1} . In the spectra of compounds 2a-e, the disappearance of signal

Scheme 1

at 1 645-1 635 cm^{-1} indicates the absence of C=O group; bands are observed at 1 605-1 600 (C=N), 1 330-1 310 (CH₂ of pyrazoline), 1 240-1 210 (C-N) and 3 350-3 340 cm^{-1} (OH).

The spectra of the compounds 3a-e show absence of signal at 1 645-1 635 cm^{-1} indicating the absence of keto group present in the chalcones 1a-e; peaks are observed at 1 625-1 600 (C=N), 1 230-1 210 (C-O-N) and 3 400-3 340 cm^{-1} (OH).

^ψPresented at the 28th Annual Convention of Chemists held at Jadavpur University, Calcutta, 1991.

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Pmr spectrum (DMSO- d_6) of **2a** shows signals at δ 2.90 (1H, dd, CH_2 of parazoline ring), 3.70 (1H, dd, CH_2 of parazoline ring), 5.0 (1H, dd, CH of pyrazoline ring) and 7.0–7.6 (m, ArH). Compound **3a** exhibited signals at δ 2.80 (1H, dd, CH_2 of isoxazoline ring), 3.60 (1H, dd, CH_2 of isoxazoline ring), 5.1 (1H, dd, CH of isoxazoline) and 6.9–7.4 (m, ArH).

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 557 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a XL-100A (100.1 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal reference standard. The purity of the compounds was checked on tlc.

1-(2'-Hydroxy-4''-n-butoxy-5'-bromophenyl)-3-aryl-2-propen-1-one (1a-e) : To a solution of 2-hydroxy-4-n-butoxy-5-bromoacetophenone (0.01 mol) and aromatic aldehyde (0.011 mol) in ethanol (50 ml), was added in portions a solution of KOH (40%; 40 ml) keeping the reaction mixture below 10° throughout. The reaction mixture was then kept for 24 h at room temperature, rendered acidic with dilute HCl (1 : 1) and poured over crushed ice. The solid thus obtained was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

1-Phenyl-3-(2''-hydroxy-4''-n-butoxy-5''-bromophenyl)-5-aryl-2-pyrazolines (2a-e) : A mixture of the chalcone (**1**; 0.005 mol) and phenylhydrazine (0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) was refluxed on an oil-bath at $110-120^\circ$ for 4 h. It was then cooled and poured in ice-water. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from 95% ethanol.

3-(2''-Hydroxy-4''-n-butoxy-5''-bromophenyl)-5-aryl-2-isoxazolines (3a-e) : A mixture of the chalcone (**1**; 0.01 mol), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.02 mol) and KOH (0.02 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and acidified

with glacial acetic acid. The resulting solid was washed and crystallised from 95% ethanol (Table 1).

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1–3*

Compd. no.	R	M.p. $^\circ C$	Yield %
1a	3,4-Dichlorophenyl	140	72
b	2-Hydroxyphenyl	70	65
c	4-Bromophenyl	146	65
d	2-Chlorophenyl	108	75
e	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	120–1	75
2a	3',4'-Dichlorophenyl	174	58
b	2'-Hydroxyphenyl	80	62
c	4'-Bromophenyl	132	70
d	2'-Chlorophenyl	115	72
e	2',4'-Dichlorophenyl	111	65
3a	3',4'-Dichlorophenyl	119	70
b	2'-Hydroxyphenyl	135	62
c	4'-Bromophenyl	124	65
d	2-Chlorophenyl	100	55
e	2',4'-Dichlorophenyl	103	55

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

Antibacterial activity : The compounds were screened for antibacterial activity by cup-plate method at a concentration of $50 \mu g ml^{-1}$ against gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* using their dimethylformamide solution. The activity was compared with chloromycetin. The results show that most of the chalcones possess moderate to good activity (zone of inhibition, 15–20 mm), while the pyrazolines and isoxazolines possess feeble activity (zone of inhibition, 5–10 mm) against both the bacteria. Some of the compounds containing chlorine/bromine atoms were active while others possessed moderate or feeble activity against both the bacteria.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the authorities of R. R. Mehta College of Science, Palanpur, for facilities. They are also grateful to the Principal, L. M. College of Pharmacy, Ahmedabad, for spectral analysis.

NOTE

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